

Complete degradation of the anionic surfactant by UV based advanced oxidation process and biodegradability

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Abstract : This work investigates the degradation of anionic surfactant (sodium dodecyl sulfate, SDS) using direct UV and UV-H₂O₂ advanced oxidation process (AOP). Direct photolysis and AOP experiments were conducted by using UV reactor that emits monochromatic light at 253.7 nm. The experiments on direct photolysis of SDS is very slow process compared to UV-H₂O₂ process. The rate constant was determined by using pseudo-first order kinetic model and rate constant was 0.8685 min⁻¹. Experiments were also carried out to observe degradation of SDS (initial concentration of 100 mg/L) in municipal wastewater spiked samples. It was found that the SDS degradation for wastewater spiked samples was slower compared to distilled water spiked samples. The pseudo-first order reaction rate constant for distilled water spiked samples was found to be 1.4 times higher compared to wastewater spiked samples. The biodegradability of intermediate products formed during degradation of SDS was examined.

Keywords : Surfactant, advanced oxidation, SDS, kinetics, UV.

I. Introduction

Continuing processes of industrialization and urbanization in association with population growth, deforestation, and pollution are increasing the discharge of recalcitrant pollutants such as surfactants, pharmaceuticals, personal care products, dyes, etc. into the environment the causing enormous ecological and public health problems. Many of them contain refractory organics, which have recently become concern of environmental engineering and hence classified as emerging contaminants, are unable to be eliminated using conventional treatment processes. Among these contaminants, surfactants are popularly used in different industries like textile, fibre, dye, personal care product paint, polymers, pharmaceutical, mining, and pulp-paper industries and domestic activities due to amphiphilic characteristics^{1,2}. For example, the average surfactant concentration in domestic wastewater is reported to be 1–10 mg/L³. Despite their utility, their persistent presence after

use is potentially hazardous and toxic to human health, as well as terrestrial and aquatic ecosystem. For example, their persistent presence in surface water below toxic levels creates several pathological, physiological, and biochemical problems on aquatic life. They cause break-down of chlorophyll-protein complex, cell death by damaging of the cell membrane and delayed metabolism or growth rate⁴. Surfactants are in four groups – anionic, cationic, zwitterionic or amphoteric and non-ionic surfactants⁵. Anionic and cationic surfactants are also called ionic surfactants. Ionic surfactants present 75% of the total surfactants. In the present study, sodium dodecyl sulfate SDS have been taken as the representative of anionic surfactants.

There are several techniques for surfactant removal from wastewater like coagulation^{6,7}, adsorption^{8,9}, reverse osmosis^{10,11} and various biological methods^{12–15}. However, all of the above methods have some limitations. For example, the reverse osmo-

sis system is expensive to install and operate. In coagulation process, a large amount of sludge is generated while adsorption process results in only phase transfer of pollutants, instead of their elimination. Biological process, on the other hand, is eco-friendly and provides for the removal of any pollutant from water environment. However, maintaining operational conditions for biological process are very difficult. Due to this fact, many researchers have explored the advanced oxidation processes (AOP) for degradation of surfactants. AOPs are based on the chemistry of hydroxyl radicals (OH^\bullet), which are non-selective reactive species being able to oxidize pollutants into mineral end-products, ultimately yielding CO_2 and inorganic ions. AOPs, include, photochemical process (O_3/UV and $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{UV}$)^{3,16-22}, photocatalytic processes (TiO_2/UV)²³⁻²⁶ and photo-Fenton process²⁷⁻³⁰ and are generally used to degrade various recalcitrant pollutants. But their applications remain limited due to high operational cost. Therefore, to overcome such limitations of the above process, in this present study we have used a treatment of a homogeneous UV- H_2O_2 AOP as a more efficient option to complete degrade the most widely used surfactants like anionic surfactant.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

Acridine orange II (ACO), glacial acetic acid, sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) (Merck, Germany), toluene and H_2O_2 were used. All other chemicals used in this study were of high purity. The strength of the hydrogen peroxide stock solution was determined by using potassium permanganate titration method.

B. Instrumentation

A high precision electrical balance (Afcoset ER-182) was used for weighing. Digital pH meter (Orion 420A+, Thermo) was used to measure pH. A spectrophotometer (single beam spectrophotometer 117, Systronics) was used to measure absorbance. UV Reactor (M/s. Lab Tree) was used for degradation of anionic surfactant (SDS).

C. UV Reactor

Direct photolysis and AOP experiments were conducted by using UV reactor (M/s. Lab Tree, India) that emits monochromatic light at 253.7 nm. The reactor comprises of eight UV tubes, fitted in a heavy metal enclosure with a stainless steel highly polished reflector. The UV photon flux was measured and monitored throughout the experiments by using potassium ferrioxalate actinometry³¹. The photon flux of the reactor was found to be $1.90 \times 10^{-05} \pm 9.66 \times 10^{-07}$ Einstein/min/100 mL.

D. Analytical method

A rapid and reliable solvent extraction spectrophotometric method is used for the determination of anionic surfactant³². Acridine orange (ACO) chemically known as 3,6-bis (dimethylamino) acridine having colour ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 467$ nm) has the potential for being used as an ion-pairing agent with anionic surfactant. Sample solution (10 mL) containing SDS in the range of 3.5×10^{-4} to 2.1×10^{-2} mM was transferred into a 25-mL separating funnel. ACO (5×10^{-3} M) and glacial acetic acid 100 μL each was added. Then 5 mL toluene was added to it and shaken for 1 min. The aqueous layer was then discarded and the toluene layer was used for absorbance measurement at 467 nm.

E. Experimental studies

Direct photolysis and advanced oxidation experiments were conducted by using batch UV reactor. All experiments were conducted using 100 mL of cationic surfactant bearing wastewater and 10 mM phosphate buffer at $27(\pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$. The samples of direct photolysis were kept in a quartz beaker with upper and lower surface been covered and irradiated for 6 h. The samples were taken at every 30 min interval analysed for percentage of degradation of SDS concentration. The kinetic equation for direct photolysis of can be SDS written as shown below :

$$\ln \frac{[\text{SDS}]}{[\text{SDS}]_0} = -k'_{\text{app}} H' \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, [SDS] is SDS concentration

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at any time t ; $[SDS]_0$ is initial SDS concentration; k'_{app} is apparent fluence based pseudo-first order reaction rate constant (cm^2/mJ) and H' is the fluence corresponding to time t (mJ/cm^2). The fluence based rate constant will be helpful to design the UV dose in the real field application. For UV- H_2O_2 process, the H_2O_2 doses was set as molar ratio of H_2O_2 to SDS. In particular, molar for ratio 2 (mol of H_2O_2 /mol of SDS) was investigated. The pH of the solution was 7 ± 0.1 . Samples were taken at regular interval from 0 to 10 min of irradiation. The experimental results were analysed by above kinetic model (eq. (1)). The effectiveness of the process was studied using municipal wastewater spiked samples. In this study, raw wastewater was collected from municipal sewer and it was filtered using commercial filter paper followed by Whatman 42 filter paper. Then the filtered water was used to prepare SDS spiked sample.

The biodegradability of intermediate products formed during degradation of SDS was examined. AOP transformed samples were tested for biodegradability. The COD and BOD of the degraded samples were measured and change in BOD to COD ratio was observed. The increase in BOD to COD ratio indicates the increase in biodegradability of the anionic surfactant.

III. Results and discussion

SDS degradation was conducted under two different experimental conditions : (1) direct photolysis, and (2) advanced oxidation process in the presence of hydrogen peroxide as discussed below.

A. Direct photolysis of SDS

The degradation of SDS was subjected to run under UV 253.7 nm with initial SDS concentration of 100 mg/L. The pH was 7.1. This degradation study was run for 6 h. Fig. 1 shows that the result of SDS degradation by UV radiation. It was noticed that only 45% degradation of SDS was achieved after 6 h.

Kinetic study was conducted to examine the rate of reaction at which UV degradation occurs. Kinetic study followed the pseudo-first order kinetic model

Fig. 1. Degradation of SDS spiked in distilled water at UV 253.7 nm.

(Fig. 2). The time-based rate constant and the fluence based rate constant were determined by using pseudo-first order kinetic model. The time-based rate constant was $2.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and the fluence based rate constant was found to be $1.77 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/mJ$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Linearized plot for first order kinetic model for direct photolysis of SDS.

B. Advanced oxidation process of SDS by UV- H_2O_2 process

From the above result, the application of UV radiation process was not rapid SDS degradation. Therefore, it can be expected that UV based AOP i.e. UV- H_2O_2 may increase the efficiency of degradation. Fig. 3 shows that SDS degradation efficiency in presence of H_2O_2 at molar ratios of 2 (mol of H_2O_2 /mol of SDS) at pH 7 and initial concentration of SDS of 100 mg/L.

Fig. 3. Degradation of SDS spiked in distilled water by UV in the presence of H_2O_2 .

It was noticed that total degradation of SDS were achieved within 4 min. From the results we noticed that the hydroxyl radical generated from UV- H_2O_2 process (i.e. 1 mol/L mol H_2O_2) was the driving force behind enhanced the degradation of SDS. The contribution of hydroxyl radicals was found to be about 100% degradation of SDS. Kinetic analysis was conducted to examine the rate of reaction of this AOP. The time-based rate constant as well as the fluence based rate constant were determined by using pseudo-first order kinetic model (Fig. 4). The time-based rate constant was 0.8586 min^{-1} and the fluence based rate constant was found to be $7.70 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{mJ}$ respectively. The rate constants found in this case were ~ 400 times more compared to SDS degradation through direct UV.

Fig. 4. Linearized plot for first order kinetic model for UV- H_2O_2 AOP of SDS.

C. Effect of municipal wastewater on SDS degradation

The SDS solution with initial concentration of 100 mg/L was prepared with filtered municipal wastewater having BOD of 200.4 mg/L, COD of 848.64 mg/L, total solids of 1334 mg/L, fixed solids of 950 mg/L and dissolved solids of 384 mg/L. The $[H_2O_2]/[SDS]$ was 2 and the pH was 7.1 ± 0.1 . The degradation of SDS by this case was found to be lesser compared to distilled water spiked samples (Fig. 5). For example, the degradation of SDS at 2 min were found to be 73 and 49% for distilled water spiked and wastewater spiked samples respectively. The fluence based rate constant for this case was found to be $5.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{mJ}$ and the time-based rate constant for this case was found to be 0.6189 min^{-1} which was found to be 1.4 times lower compared to the rate constant found in case of distilled water spiked samples at pH 7. This might be due to the presence of natural alkalinity in wastewater which acted as scavenger of hydroxyl radical.

Fig. 5. Degradation of SDS spiked in municipal wastewater by UV in the presence of H_2O_2 .

The BOD to COD ratio of the UV- H_2O_2 transformation products has been shown in Fig. 6. It was found that BOD to COD ratio increased with time. In particular, 100 mg/L SDS solutions were treated by UV- H_2O_2 for 2, 4, 6, and 8 min. Residual H_2O_2 in the treated samples was quenched by catalase before measurement of COD and BOD_5 . The initial

Fig. 6. Increase in biodegradability for UV-H₂O₂ degraded 100 mg/L SDS.

BOD₅/COD ratio for 100 mg/L of SDS solution was found to be 0.12 (± 0.02), indicating that SDS is not biodegradable. BOD₅/COD fraction is increasing from 0.12 to 0.6 fraction within 8 min of degradation for 100 mg/L of SDS. Further, it is to be noted that the initial BOD₅ of 100 mg/L SDS solution is 30 mg/L and it has increased to 90 mg/L after 8 min of UV-H₂O₂ treatment. These results demonstrate that the transformation products were more biodegradable than the SDS parent compound. Therefore, BOD₅/COD ratio in UV-H₂O₂ treated effluent was 0.602, the effluent can be effectively treated by biological processes.

IV. Conclusions

Advanced oxidation process could effectively be used for the degradation of recalcitrant pollutants like anionic surfactants. The direct photolysis was found to be very slow in degrading the cationic surfactant. Only 45% degradation of SDS (initial concentration 100 mg/L) was observed through direct UV process in 6 h. However, for the UV-H₂O₂ process, more than 100% transformation of SDS was achieved with a fluence and peroxide dose of 450 mJ/cm² and 2 mol H₂O₂/mol SDS respectively. Degradation of SDS spiked in municipal wastewater was slower compared to distilled water spiked samples. The rate constants for distilled water spiked samples was found to be 1.4 times higher compared to municipal wastewater spiked samples. This might be due to scavenging of hydroxyl radicals by the con-

stituents of wastewater. Finally, the UV-H₂O₂ process provides quick and efficient transformation of anionic surfactant that can be applied in real field.

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